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Abstract

In the context of this bachelor thesis, the interaction with virtual prototypes in Mixed Reality is investigated.

The main content of this thesis consists of two parts. The development of three interactions to operate the virtual prototypes of the Vivian Framework with the HoloLens 2 and the subsequent evaluation of these in a usability study. The study is carried out with two groups. One group is instructed in the interaction possibilities, the other group explores them intuitively. The suitability of the interactions as well as how they can be improved based on the results of the usability study are examined.

In summary, the following results arise. The hand interaction is particularly suitable for pressing buttons or placing objects in a designated place. The pointer interaction is suitable for touching and moving objects that are further away. The head interaction is rather unsuitable for interacting with small objects. Compared to the other interactions, this interaction requires the least effort to move objects.

Kurzfassung

Im Rahmen dieser Bachelorarbeit wird die Interaktion mit virtuellen Prototypen in Mixed Reality untersucht.

Der Hauptbestandteil dieser Arbeit besteht aus zwei Teilen. Der Entwicklung von drei Interaktionen, mit welchen die virtuellen Prototypen des Vivian Frameworks mithilfe der HoloLens 2 bedient werden können und im Anschluss die Evaluierung dieser in einer Usability Studie. Diese wird mit zwei Gruppen durchgeführt. Die eine Gruppe erhält eine Einweisung in die Interaktionsmöglichkeiten, die andere Gruppe soll diese intuitiv erforschen. Es wird die Eignung der Interaktionen untersucht, sowie wie diese anhand der Ergebnisse der Usability Studie verbessert werden können.

Zusammengefasst ergeben sich die folgenden Ergebnisse. Die Handinteraktion eignet sich besonders für das Drücken von Tasten oder das Ablegen von Objekten an einem bestimmten Ort. Die Pointerinteraktion eignet sich für das Berühren und Bewegen von weiter entfernten Objekten. Die Kopferinteraktion ist eher ungeeignet, um mit kleinen Objekten zu interagieren. Im Vergleich zu den anderen Interaktionen erfordert diese Interaktion den geringsten Aufwand, um Objekte zu bewegen.

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1 Introduction

Virtual prototyping is crucial these days. Global competition is forcing industries to constantly optimise products and shorten time-to-market in order to be competitive. [1] A clear competitive advantage is the innovativeness of a product. However, if an equivalent product from another company enters the market before, the profits that would have been brought in with an innovative product can no longer be achieved.

Virtual Prototyping (VP) speeds up the development process and allows user tests at an early stage to address their needs. Because VP is such an important part of the development process, software is being developed with new possibilities and to optimise these processes for this purpose. An example of this is the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) software developed by the company CADLOG [2], for the development of products in the field of fluid mechanics. This software is applied in research, studies, and industries, including aerodynamics, aerospace, and environmental engineering. [3]

The basis of virtual prototypes are 3D models of objects that are provided with functions. Before these can be tested, a few steps are necessary in between. These include modelling, animation, assigning functions and making the object available on a device on which it has to be tested. If the object has to be tested with a computer mouse, then the interaction development looks different than if the object has to for example be tested via a smartphone or virtual reality glasses.

The Vivian Framework [4] aims to shorten the process from the creation of the prototype to the operation of the prototype and to provide the interaction in the entire Extended Reality [5]. This work is motivated by providing interaction with virtual prototypes of the Vivian Framework in Mixed Reality with the Microsoft HoloLens 2 [6]. Therefore, the focus of this work is the implementation and evaluation of these interactions.

2 Foundations

2.1 Mixed Reality

As the name implies, mixed reality (MR) stands for a mixed reality. This refers to a mixture of the real reality and a virtually generated reality. Mixed reality is the merge of human, computer, and environment. In this way, the real environment is actively incorporated and not as a kind of veil over objects of the real reality as in Augmented Reality (AR) or as in Virtual Reality (VR) that the real reality is no longer perceived directly. MR involves the real environment. [7]

AR and VR are parts of the MR spectrum. This implies varying degrees of integration of virtual elements which can be embedded in the MR. Individual objects can be pinned to the user's field of vision and follow the user as they move around or be placed in the room permanently. So, when the user leaves the room, the object is no longer visible. The appearance of real walls can also be changed. This enables a virtual reality that blends in with the real environment and replaces it, creating the mixed reality. [8]

2.2 Virtual Prototypes

A technical product goes through a long development process before it is mass produced. Since the purpose of technical devices is to be used by people, it is important to choose the best product design and to eliminate possible deficiencies evaluating it. For this reason, prototypes of these prospective products are created, tested, and continuously developed according to the principles of usability engineering. An essential goal of this is to avoid unnecessary complexity and to reduce the functionality of a product to an ideal minimum for the user [9, p. 7] to develop a self-explanatory design.

This process takes a long time and is accordingly associated with costs. Virtual prototypes (VP) have the advantage that the step of continuous creation of physical prototypes can be reduced, and they can be adapted with comparatively less effort and at a lower cost. This allows users to actively participate in the development process and to validate the product design and test it for usability, ergonomics, and comfort already in the initial phase. [10, p. 8f]

The Aberdeen Group [11], a market research company, has published a report showing clear results on the impact of virtual prototyping in leading manufacturing companies. Figure 2 shows the difference between virtual and physical prototypes in terms of quality, revenue, launch time and cost. [1]

Have you achieved your design goals?

Source: Aberdeen Group

Figure 1 The advantaged of virtual prototyping [11]

2.3 Vivian Framework

Vivian is a technical framework for deploying and operating virtual prototypes in Extended Reality (XR), based on a single configuration.

The Vivian Framework consists of two phases. In the first phase, the VP is extended to include a functional specification. This requires marking the model components that represent interaction and visualisation elements. In addition, element specific configuration parameters are specified. Afterwards, the state machine is defined with the intended functionalities of the device. In the second phase, the VPs with specifications are utilised in XR to deploy and to interact with them. The Vivian Framework provides respective runtime environments for this purpose. [4]

The Vivian Framework is implemented using the Unity Engine. In the engine, it consists of the Vivian Framework script and the Virtual Prototype script. The prototype is selected via the Bundle URL and the Prototype Prefab Name, as figure 2 depicts.

Figure 2 Vivian Framework - Unity Inspector view

The prototype is available in the scene during runtime when the play button is activated. Only then the script invokes selected the prototype. Loading during runtime means that the prototypes do not have to be loaded individually onto the device. All the necessary components an object needs to interact are added with the script. This procedure accelerates the process from the creation to the operation of virtual prototypes.

2.4 HoloLens 2

The device used in here to access MR is the HoloLens 2, a mixed reality headset from Microsoft. It is a standalone device, which means that it does not require a connection to a PC and functions autonomously. Among other things, the device is equipped with integrated voice commands, eye tracking and world anchors. Thanks to the world anchors, digital content remains where it is placed, even over time. The hand tracking enables a natural way to interact with holograms. With the help of voice commands, even hands-free operation is possible. [12] The diverse possibilities and limitless remote collaboration in real time [13], enable use in industry, research, and medicine, for example.

Microsoft provides an extensive documentation for the development with the HoloLens, beginning with the first use. Among other things, for the recording of visual material via the device directly [14] as well as a Microsoft companion app [15] for establishing a connection with the HoloLens and the possibility of a live stream. These options are also used in this work.

2.5 Mixed Reality Toolkit

The Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK) is a project driven by Microsoft. With a set of components and functions such as input systems, hand tracking, eye tracking, UX building blocks, this is intended to accelerate the development of cross-platform MR applications in Unity. In addition, there are example scenes in which the various functions can be explored directly. All components and the handling of them are documented in detail. [16]

With the MRTK, all kinds of components such as the different input systems can be added and adapted according to one's own needs. In this work, however, these cannot be applied. This is because the prototypes are loaded in during runtime. When the components are added to the Virtual Framework, they are perceived as a whole and the individual components, such as buttons or doors, can no longer be controlled, alienating the purpose. Therefore, in this work, interactions are programmed that use the MRTK and access the interaction triggers of the prototypes.

2.6 Usability

A main component of this thesis is the usability evaluation of the resulting interactions. This chapter is intended to clarify the meaning of usability.

Usability must be evaluated in the context of its use. Good usability can be understood as a quality indicator for the designed user interface, but not only a coherent user interface is important. The functions in the application should be easy and efficient for users to use. Usability is related to how well users can use the tool to accomplish the task. The definition of it is therefore set by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). [17, p. 10f]

In this context, the focus of the usability of this work is on the usability of the interactions. Looking at how one part of the test subjects uses the interactions intuitively and the other part with instructions. In addition, attention is paid to which dysfunctions of the interactions occur during the tests. These results serve as a basis to optimise them for better usability.

3 State of the Art

The Vivian Framework is the first one focusing explicitly on deploying and operating VPs in XR. For this reason, methods that are primarily related to Mixed Reality and interaction are considered here. As was already made clear in the foundations, MR is similar to VR and interaction with VR is mainly known from the field of game development. Consequently, the possibilities that are possible in games are also possible in MR, with the difference that this technology integrates the real environment. It should be emphasised that MR games such as RoboRaid or Fragments [18] are also created with the development of the HoloLens.

A similar concept is that of the digital twin. With a digital twin, the technical or physical components can be tested long before the manufacturing process. It should be noted that these do not fully represent the original, but are rather reproduced in digital form . [19, p. 2] This technique is used by Siemens [20], Bosch [21] und Fraunhofer [22] for example.

What differentiates the Vivian framework from the other technologies, is that it aims to shorten the process to actual interaction and at the same time offer it throughout the XR.

4 Approach

4.1 Targets and Requirements Analysis

The target of this bachelor thesis is the interaction with virtual prototypes of the Vivian Framework via the HoloLens 2. Microsoft provides the framework called Mixed Reality Toolkit for such purposes. This framework is also used in this project for the mixed reality environment and the user interface elements. The interactions in this case, however, are limited in their applicability to the virtual prototypes. This is because these virtual prototypes are part of the Vivian Framework. The Vivian Framework and its benefits are described in more detail in chapter 2.3. The characteristic of the mentioned software is that the prototypes are loaded only in the Play Mode into the scene. If one wants to add the components with the interactions, then it is possible to apply these only to the framework. Doing that, the prototypes can only be moved as a whole, which alienates the purpose. In this way, the individual components of the prototypes such as buttons or individual objects such as mugs cannot be used.

For this reason, the goal of this thesis is to develop interactions that respond to the individual functions of the prototypes.

Must-have criteria:

- The components of the virtual prototypes of the Vivian framework respond to interaction.
- The prototypes of the Vivian Framework are operated via the HoloLens 2.
- Evaluation of the application by test persons in a usability study.

Optional criteria:

- Comparison between different interaction types.
- Menu for testing multiple prototypes without interruption.

4.2 Project Base

For this work, the freely available Vivian Windows Test project is used. This is added to Unity Hub and the version of the Unity project is changed to 2019.4. Unity is a real-time development platform from the company Unity Technologies for developing interactive applications. The best-known area of use is in game development, but the engine also gives many companies a competitive advantage in industry. [23]

After opening the Vivian Windows Test project in Unity, the MRTK foundations package version 2.5.1 is first imported, and the default settings are applied to adapt the environment for development for HoloLens. Afterwards, the MRTK is applied to each scene, thus converting it into an MR scene.

4.3 Hand Interaction

First the hand interaction is created with the purpose of touching objects directly with one's own hand. To be able to use one's own hands, these must be recognised as such and precisely tracked during runtime. The Mixed Reality Toolkit, which is described in more detail in chapter 2.6, provides the hand tracking components used in this project. How this individual hand interaction is developed follows now.

The hand interaction contains three elements. A mesh collider, a rigidbody, and the Hand Interaction Handler script with a sphere marker. The mesh collider and rigidbody are necessary since a sphere marker is used here to create a collision with prototypes. The Mesh Collider adjusts the shape of the visible mesh for the GameObject, allowing for more precise collisions. However, when using it, it is important to note that it is only one-sided. This allows a GameObject to pass through one side and a collision only occurs on the other side. [24] This is visible, for example, in the scene with the microwave. The pie can only be grabbed from below.

If the cake is grabbed from above, it does not react. Rigidbodies allow GameObjects to behave according to the laws of physics. For the collision between two rigidbodies to be calculated, both need colliders, as mentioned above. Otherwise, both simply pass each other without colliding. [25] The setting of this rigidbody is that the detection of the collision is continuous.

The Hand Interaction Handler script uses four namespaces. Namespaces are collections of classes that are referred to with a specific prefix for the class name. This *using* directive makes it redundant to specify the namespace name for each class. [26] [27] The following namespaces are used in this HandInteractionHandler class. UnityEngine, Microsoft.MixedReality.Toolkit.Utilities, Microsoft.MixedReality.Toolkit.Input and de.ugoe.cs.vivian.core. UnityEngine is the namespace of the Unity Engine used to develop this project. The two namespaces from Microsoft, as already mentioned in the name, are components of the MRTK, enabling hand tracking here. The namespace de.ugoe.cs.vivian core belongs to the Vivian Framework, providing the prototypes and enabling interaction with the individual components of these prototypes.

The namespaces are followed by the class of the script. Once the script has been created with the class name given, it automatically contains the MonoBehaviour class after a colon. This is the base class from which every Unity script derives. In the case like in this work, when the programming language C# is used, it must be explicitly derived from MonoBehaviour. [28]

The content of this script is structured as follows. The declared variables are listed first in this class, which are used in the following methods. Next is the Start() method, which is called before any of the update methods are called for the first time, followed by the Update() method, called for each frame when MonoBehaviour is activated, and finally three OnTrigger...() methods.

In the Start() method, the GameObject sphereMarker is instantiated and is set equal to the indexObject. The Update() method checks whether there is an interaction. Here, the HandJointUtils of the MRTK are accessed, more precisely the tracked index fingertips. Only if these are present, the indexObject is enabled.

The three trigger methods are used to access the triggers of the prototypes. There is the OnTriggerEnter(), OnTriggerStay() and OnTriggerExit() method. All three methods use the collider. This OnTriggerEnter() method is called when a collider has entered the trigger. If the OnTriggerEnter(Collider collider) method is triggered with the collision on a prototype, the TriggerInteractionStarts method of the Virtual Prototype script is accessed and set to InInteraction. If this interaction continues, the OnTriggerStay(Collider collider) method is called, which passes on to the prototype that this interaction is continuing. As soon as the collision with the prototype is interrupted, the OnTriggerExit(Collider collider) method is called. This passes the ending of the interaction with the prototype.

Figure 3 Execution of the hand interaction

The interaction can be executed with both the right and the left hand. The fingertip of the index finger is essential for this. To press a button, it is made by tapping it with the fingertip. To move an object, it is touched, moved to the desired position, and put down by pulling the hand away faster.

4.4 Pointer Interaction

The pointer interaction is intended to function like an interaction with a controller, with the difference that instead of a controller, the own hands have the function. This interaction consists only of a Pointer Interaction Handler script with the namespaces of UnityEngine, MRTK and Vivian Frameworks already mentioned in chapter 4.3.

This script consists of three methods. The Update() method, IndexFingerCurl() method and CalculateCurl() method. The two methods for calculating the curl of the finger are used from the MRTK PointerInteractionHandler script. In this Update() method, the pointer for both hands is instantiated from the MRTK PointerUtils [29].

In the Update() method, the conditions for the interaction are set. The interaction starts if there has been no interaction before and the finger has a curl greater than 0.1. If the interaction and

the curl already exists, this means that the interaction continues. If the finger is no longer curled, but the interaction is still active at that time, it is now terminated. This is because the condition for the interaction is that the finger is curled during the interaction.

Figure 4 Execution of the pointer interaction

The pointer interaction works as follows. A laser pointer rises from the palm of the hand. Objects can be targeted with this pointer. If the laser pointer hits an object, this collision is detected. To trigger the interaction, the index finger is required as well. If the finger is straight, nothing happens. If the finger is curled and points with the pointer at an element, the interaction is activated. As long as the finger remains curled, this interaction continues. Opening the index finger the interaction ends.

4.5 Head Interaction

This interaction has almost the same structure as the pointer interaction. In this script, an additional namespace is used, namely the `Microsoft.MixedReality.Toolkit`. This is needed to be able to use the Gaze Pointer. As already mentioned, this using directive makes it redundant to specify the namespace name for each class.

In this `Update()` method, the gaze pointer is instantiated from the MRTK core services from its input system. The instantiation of the interaction component is the only point where the interaction with the pointer and with the head differentiate.

Figure 5 Execution of the head interaction

In this interaction, there is no visual support to recognise whether an object is grasped with the centre of the field of vision. On the one hand, this makes it more difficult to detect, but on the other hand, the view is not permanently disturbed. Therefore, this does not tend to serve very small objects. If an object is in the centre of the field of vision and the index finger is curled, the targeted objects can be moved. With the help of this interaction, objects can be moved over longer distances with ease. To use it, an object must be aimed, the finger curled, then keeping the finger curled, moving the head until the object reaches the desired position. As soon as the finger is extended, the object stops moving. It is sufficient to just move the finger, the hand does not need to point at anything. The aiming is done only with the head. The HoloLens 2 recognises the hands as soon as they are in front of the body.

4.6 User Interface

To test several scenes seamlessly one by one, an additional scene was created. This scene, called Menu, contains a user interface to access the individual scenes.

In the Menu scene, an empty GameObject was created into which the user interface was embedded. This GameObject was again named Menu since it is the main component of the scene. This GameObject enables a script to be attached to it, which in turn can be used for all elements within it. The namespaces `UnityEngine` and `UnityEngine.SceneManagement` are used in this script. This script contains one method for each scene accessing the `SceneManager`. All desired scenes must be inserted via the *Build Setting* in Unity to be capable of loading as the figure 6 shows.

Figure 6 Build Settings - Scenes in Build

The embedded user interface contains six buttons, which form an overview of the provided scenes and a title animating to select a scene. Additionally, a button was built into each scene to navigate back to the overview. In both cases, the available UI elements of the MRTK were accessed and customized.

Figure 7 Menu - Unity View

To assign the desired function to the respective button, the existing `OnClick()` event of the MRTK button and the Runtime Only condition is used. The script of the `GameObjects` menu is dragged to the place of the empty object of the button event and the respective function was selected, which the button should trigger on a click.

Figure 8 Menu - `OnClick()` Event

The button navigating back to the overview also contains a `GameObject` and accesses the same script. It works the same way, except that it is located in the respective scene of the prototype.

5 Usability Study

5.1 Target of Evaluation

In this thesis, three interactions were programmed for the Vivian Framework. These three interactions will be evaluated in this study in scenes with the virtual prototypes. This involves investigating which interaction option feels as natural as possible to the subjects, which can be handled well, and which ones they are less successful with. During this process, attention is paid to which interaction options may be more suitable for certain activities and which ones are not.

The three interaction options evaluated in this study are the interactions with hand, a pointer, and head. These interactions are described in more detail in chapters 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5.

5.2 Subjects of the Present Study

Test subjects form an important basis for usability tests. Insights are already gathered with the first participant. According to Jakob Nielsen, the best results are achieved by testing with no

more than five users. Otherwise, resources are wasted, and the same mistakes are repeated without new insights. [30]

Ten people were evaluated for the usability study of this thesis, which were divided into two groups of five people each. The evaluation item is tested under different conditions. All participants should have at least basic experience and be confident handling smart devices, such as smartphones or computers, and be interested in new technologies.

The selected participants are between 20 and 34 years old, predominantly students and professionals who have not yet had any to extensive experience with extended reality, such as with development of games in virtual reality.

5.3 Test Execution

The test consists of a pre-session-interview with a briefing, the usability tests in the main part and a final interview. The test procedure is explained in the following.

The subjects mentioned in the last section were divided into two groups. Five of the participants were assigned to group A and the other five to group B. Participants with and without extended reality experience were equally divided between these two groups.

Group A did not receive any information on how to operate the prototypes, only that there are several interaction options, and they had to explore them by themselves.

Group B was told that there are the three previously mentioned interaction methods.

All participants in both groups tested all six scenes and were asked to do the same tasks. They were tested separately one by one and had the instruction to think aloud during the execution. This instruction is called concurrent think aloud.

This Concurrent Think Aloud (CTA) research method is used in usability tests. While the subjects perform the tasks and think aloud, it is easier for the test administrator to understand what the subjects are dealing with at the moment and what difficulties they are having or what is causing these difficulties. [31] In this way, support can be provided during this time in order to complete the further tests, as well as to evaluate the recordings at a later time if they are recorded at the same time.

5.3.1 Pre-Session-Interview and Introduction

Before a briefing by the test administrator, the subjects were asked to provide information about themselves in a short interview. In addition to their age, the subjects were asked to give their own assessment of how much they deal with technology in their professional or private lives.

Furthermore, they were asked to share their level of experience with mixed reality and what that experience has been so far. This was followed by a standardized introduction by the test administrator.

This looks as follows:

- The topic of today's usability study is interaction with virtual prototypes in mixed reality. For this we are using the HoloLens 2 from Microsoft.
- Your task here is to operate a few virtual prototypes. In doing so, I followed what you see live. In addition, your view and voice will be recorded.
- Please think aloud as much as possible. This is helpful for the evaluation and if necessary, I can offer you some support.
- When you put on the HoloLens, you will find yourself in the HoloLens menu and will launch the application itself. This way, the scene will be set up right at your eye level so you can see all the prototypes well and the eye calibration will be suggested automatically. As soon as the eye calibration is finished, please say "Start recording", at the end of the tests stop the recording by saying "Stop recording".
- You will see a menu in front of you with an overview of the scenes to be tested. We will go through all the scenes in order from left to right in the following. As soon as you have started a scene, you will receive instructions on what to do in this scene.
- The focus of this study is on the interactions that have been programmed for this purpose.
- To the participants of group A only:
 - You, as a Group A subject, do not receive any instructions about what the interaction options are. What you learn is that there are three interaction options. For this reason, please explore what is possible in order to do that.
- To the participants of group B only:
 - You, as the subject of group B, receive guidance about which interaction options have been implemented, namely the following three:
 - You can interact with the hand, more precisely with the fingertip of your index finger
 - You can interact with a pointer. Here you see a laser pointing forward from your hand, and to trigger it, you curl your index finger.
 - You sight an object with the midpoint of your field of view and to trigger this interaction, you curl your finger as in the second interaction option. As long as your finger is curled, the interaction continues. As soon as you stretch your finger, the interaction ends.
- With the different scenes, try all the interactions.

- Now let's put on the HoloLens and customize it for your head, and we can start immediately.

5.3.2 Tests

Figure 9 Menu - selecting a scene

All subjects are asked to test the same six scenes, which they access via the menu shown in figure 9. The corresponding tasks and the challenges of these scenes are described in this chapter.

Toaster scene

Task: “Place two toasts in the toaster, turn the button clockwise and turn the toaster on.”

Figure 10 Toaster scene

The challenges of this task are grabbing the toasts for the very first time, holding them and turning them to insert them into the toaster. Subsequently, the test persons have to turn a button to adjust the toast duration and push down a lever to switch on the toaster.

Microwave scene

Task: “Heat the drink in the microwave and then the cake.”

Figure 11 Microwave scene

The main challenge of this task is to operate the door while objects are in close reach, namely in the microwave or by placing them inside. In addition, due to the mesh collider and the property, as already described in chapter 4.3, the plate can only be gripped from below, not from above. Thus, the cake can be placed in the microwave with the hand interaction only by holding it from below like a real plate.

Coffee machine scene

Task: “Turn on the coffee machine and make a coffee.”

Figure 12 Coffee machine scene

This scene focuses on how the test subjects cope with particularly small buttons.

Remote scene

Task: “Turn on the TV and click through the channels.”

Figure 13 Remote control scene

The challenge in this scene is to operate an object, in this case a remote control, which itself is not anchored in the room.

Car-infotainment scene

Task: “Turn on the radio and change the radio station. Then navigate to Travel Information.”

Figure 14 Car-infotainment scene

In this scene the focus is on operating a touch screen.

Test scene

Task: "Turn half of the lights to green."

Figure 15 Test scene

In this scene there are many buttons to press, to turn, as well as large and small sliders. The test persons were encouraged to try out all the interactions again and, in the case of group A, the interactions that they had recognised in the course of the previous tests.

5.3.3 Post-Session-Interview

The post-session interview is an essential step in the scope of a usability study. In this case, this step is performed with the help of a questionnaire. The subjects answered the questions directly after the usability tests. This serves to capture the subjects' point of view. The subjects receive a questionnaire with ten questions.

Among the other questions, the subjects were asked to use a scale to rate how intuitive they found the prototypes' operation, whether they could get used to this operation, whether they would have liked more support, and whether they thought the virtual prototypes could keep up with physical prototypes. On this scale of one to five, one represents "No, not at all." and five represents "Yes, definitely." Similarly, they were asked to mark which interaction option felt most natural to them. Questions such as what the subjects liked or disliked have a long answer text area for precise elaboration. The complete questionnaires of all subjects can be found in the appendix.

6 Evaluation of the Usability Study

In this section, the evaluation of the usability study follows. Group A and Group B are considered individually. Sections 6.1 and 6.2 focus on the subjects' point of view. Sections 6.3 and 6.4 are dedicated to the observations of the test administrator. All questionnaires and tables, which serve as the basis for this evaluation, can be found in the appendix.

6.1 Post-Session-Interview Group A

The participants in group A, who did not receive instructions on the interactions, experienced the operation of the prototypes only moderately intuitive up to not intuitive at all. The average scores on a scale of one to five, with one representing "No, not at all." and five represents "Yes, definitely." resulting in a two.

Relating to the question of if they could get used to this way of operating, the views of the testers were different. Figure 16 illustrates these differences.

Könnten Sie sich an die Bedienweise gewöhnen?

5 Antworten

Figure 16 Questionnaire question: "Could you get used to the operating method?"

The participants would have preferred more support during the tests. Without exception, they experienced the interaction with the hand as the most natural. This result is up to expectations, as this is our natural way of operating real objects.

The participants would have liked to have events explained in more detail that they created themselves, as well as how exactly to operate the prototypes. Disappearing objects and problems when releasing, were mentioned repeatedly. When asked if virtual prototypes could compete with physical prototypes, 60% of respondents in this group were in the middle range, neither agreeing nor disagreeing.

The existing audio feedback was well received and more need for audio feedback was expressed. Primarily, the aspects that are best received are those that make the experience most realistic. This includes the direct interaction with the hand, the prototypes of ordinary objects, as well as the fact that the real environment has been extended with these 3D models.

6.2 Post-Session-Interview Group B

The participants in group B, who received instructions on the interactions, experienced the operation of the prototypes moderately intuitive. The experiences are in none of the extrama and even two of the five tested subjects rate the operation of the prototypes as well intuitive.

When asked whether the test subjects could get used to the way of operating the device, the results are similarly wide ranging as with the previous group, with a tendency that they could get used to it rather less well. Four of the five test subjects found the introduction very helpful and would have wished for little to no additional support. Despite this indication, a few of the testers expressed in the free text area that a tutorial with demonstration and training on how to perform the gestures exactly would make the experience more pleasant for them. Among other things, they were sometimes unable to distinguish the pointer interaction from the head interaction, or caused objects to disappear due to incorrect execution. One subject felt that the curvature of the finger needed to trigger the interaction was too small.

When asked if virtual prototypes could compete with physical prototypes, 80% of the respondents in this group voted a four out of five on the scale mentioned earlier.

Also in this group, the test subjects without exception felt that the interaction with the hand was the most natural. One of the things mentioned here was that this interaction is much more comfortable for the hand compared to the others, as the fingers tend to cramp up during the other interactions. Despite this favourite interaction, the multiple possibilities for interacting with an object were rated positively. One test person stated that the hand interaction is best suited for pressing buttons and the pointer interaction for moving objects.

6.3 Observations Group A

In this chapter, the evaluation of group A, which consists of five test subjects follows, which did not receive any briefing on the existing types of interaction. All scenes are considered individually. Special attention is paid to the challenges of each scene already mentioned in the description and whether the implemented interactions will be recognized.

Toaster scene

Two of the test subjects experienced difficulties in grabbing the toasts with their hands. The difficulties were due to the fingers being too curved, which unintentionally triggered the pointer interaction, causing the toast to jump away and disappear. Two people successfully grasped the toast with their hand and put it into the toaster. However, it happened to both subjects that they took out at least one toast unintentionally. Unintentional removal of toast slices from the toaster occurred with pointer and head interaction by four of the test subjects of this group.

Two of the test subjects successfully inserted toasts with the pointer interaction without removing them shortly afterwards. By two subjects, moving and inserting the toasts into the toaster with the head was not done with full intention. This can be seen from the fact that the people tried to use the pointer interaction or said it out loud during the process. The button was rotated by only two people, namely with their finger. Turning on the toaster was also done with the finger. Three people managed to do this, while one unintentionally removed a toast in the process.

In this scene, it was obvious that many interactions happened unintentionally due to a bent finger position. On the one hand, this was because some people naturally tend to handle with closed hands and, on the other hand, due to the movement of grabbing. After a little practice, most of the test subjects were able to handle the toast slices well. Even though it was not done intentionally, it led to the completion of the tasks.

Microwave scene

First, the microwave was turned on using the finger directly, without exception. This was expected, as this motion is very intuitive, especially after practicing direct interaction with one's own hand in the previous scene.

Two people opened the door with the pointer, two with the head interaction. One subject managed to open the door just a crack with its finger.

If we consider the mugs and pies handled by all the test persons in this scene, this results in 10 objects. This shows that about 30% of the objects were moved with the finger, 20% with the pointer and 30% with the head. For the remaining 20%, the objects were lost during the interaction.

Three people closed the door with the pointer. Two closed the door with their finger, but one of them needed several attempts.

Coffee machine scene

This scene focuses on how the test subjects cope with particularly small buttons. All the people managed to turn on the coffee machine and make a coffee. Only one person needed several attempts to press the buttons and two of the subjects had to do the coffee without a cup, since they have lost it.

It is also worth noting that one test person consciously and successfully used head interaction to move the cup.

Remote scene

In this scene, one problem becomes clear. Among all the testers, the remote control gets stuck on their finger. Be it when grasping it or switching it on. Only one person managed to both switch on the TV and change channels.

Car-infotainment scene

The task was successfully completed by all subjects. In this scene, finger interaction was used without exception to operate the touch screen. This worked immediately for all participants.

Test scene

In this scene with many buttons to press, to turn, as well as large and small sliders only the hand interaction was used, with one exception. This exception refers to one participant who moved a slider with the pointer interaction. All other participants used only the hand interaction. Two of them were able to interact with both types of buttons and the sliders. The other three only to a limited extent.

6.4 Observations Group B

Group B follows received a briefing on the existing types of interaction. All scenes are considered individually. Special attention is given to the challenges of each scene already mentioned, the execution of the interactions and the interactions themselves.

Toaster scene

Two subjects in this group successfully completed the task with the hand interaction. This includes grabbing, holding, and placing the toast in the toaster, as well as turning a button and pressing a lever to turn it on. The other three subjects had the same repetitive difficulties. They repeatedly failed to place the toast in the toaster or accidentally removed it from the toaster shortly afterwards. These three subjects who failed at first tried the interactions that were explained to them at the beginning. Finally, two more subjects, this time with the pointer interaction, were also successful in inserting the toasts into the toaster. The button and lever were also done by hand by these subjects.

One subject was overwhelmed with this task and was unable to achieve the goal of this task despite additional assistance. What made the interaction difficult, was the subjects posture. Initially, the subject held the hands at the front of its body and thus unintentionally triggered the pointer and head interaction but was unable to use them intentionally. So, the toast slices were brought to the toaster with the hands and lost there. The button was turned with the finger. The lever was only moved briefly by mistake and the toaster was not switched on.

In this scene 40% of this group handled the hand interaction well. The other 40% found that they were better able to handle the pointer interaction in this task than the direct hand interaction.

Microwave scene

First, the microwave was turned on using the finger directly, without exception. Two persons opened the door with the finger, two with the head interaction and one with the pointer interaction.

40% of the objects were successfully moved with the hand interaction to complete the task. Likewise, 40% of the objects were moved with the pointer interaction. The remaining 20% is a result of the items being lost along the way during the hand interaction and the head interaction.

When closing the door, three subjects used the finger interaction and two used the pointer interaction. While one test person had difficulties closing the door with the pointer.

Coffee machine scene

One subject placed the cup onto the coffee machine using the head interaction. The four others chose the hand interaction. Two of the four subjects who chose the hand interaction had the following dilemma. One subject lost the cup when touching it, the other could not put it down directly.

Pressing the small buttons was easy for four of the subjects. One test person first moved his finger inside the coffee machine. In this way, the button was not triggered until the person pressed the button again from the outside.

Remote scene

In this scene, primarily the hand interaction was used. Only one test person performs a single action with the pointer, namely turning on the TV.

When the remote control is touched, it gets stuck on the subject's finger. This happens when even the switch-on button is pressed directly. In the case of one participant, the power button did not react. Apart from this one glitch, all the other test subjects achieved the goal of this task and successfully switched through the channels.

The errors encountered in this test provide useful clues for improving the hand interaction.

Car-infotainment scene

Only two of the participants completed the task without any obstacles. The other three subjects had, among other things, image dropouts, difficulty activating the button and a lack of reaction from the touch display. Among other things, the travel information was selected without conscious interaction, which was possibly triggered by the head interaction. The difficulty in pressing the button could be due to the image dropouts.

Test scene

In this test, all subjects used the finger interaction. One of them additionally used the pointer interaction for the buttons and the sliders. The buttons were pressed by the four participants, but for one of them they did not seem to react. The buttons and sliders were manipulated with the finger by all subjects.

During one test, the hand tracking was not tracked correctly, and was beside the real hand.

The buttons were turned only slightly in terms of rotation. This is since buttons with this shape are usually gripped differently and this way of gripping, namely with the side of the finger and the tip of the thumb, is not developed.

7 Discussion

This section explains the results of this usability study. Differences between the subjects without an instruction compared to those with one and how the interactions compare are examined in more detail.

Looking at the first test scene with the toaster, it is evident that both groups have equal initial difficulties. In both groups, there are subjects who are able to complete the tasks and those who have difficulties doing so. The main difference is that the subjects in group A more often use interactions unintentionally and as a result interfere with the interaction with their own hand. Due to the prior instruction of group B, these participants notice when they use one of the two interactions.

Among the common occurrences is the curvature of the fingers while grabbing an object. This is an obstructive reflex in the interaction that the curvature of the index fingers is used to trigger the other two interactions. According to reports here, a larger curvature would be better to avoid accidentally triggering these interactions. During the development process, a larger finger curvature was tried out, but was found to be uncomfortable, as the finger then has to be curved more strongly, as targeted. Through the insights of the usability tests, it becomes clear that some people tend to keep their fingers rather curved when not active. At this point, it is important to mention that if the subjects perform an interaction differently than planned, it must be further developed to generate an optimal user experience. Therefore, it makes sense to adjust the curvature of the index fingers again in the future and to test with which finger curvature this is no longer done accidentally.

It is interesting that even when the subjects in group A do not intentionally use the interactions with the pointer and the head, at least initially, these interactions still lead to the completion of the task. This aspect indicates intuitive handling of the interactions. Providing the user receives clear, visual, or auditory feedback.

In the scene with the toaster, it becomes clear for the first time that some of the subjects are more comfortable interacting directly with the hand and some with the pointer. This shows why many interaction possibilities are advantageous as people have their own preferences. In other scenes, these results are confirmed when interacting with similar elements, such as moving a cup or a door. The head interaction is also consciously used by both groups to move objects in further scenes. This shows that all three interactions are well suited for moving objects and even people who have not received instructions can use them well after a short familiarisation phase. Occasionally, one person in a group had greater difficulties in a test. It is important to emphasise that this was not at all the same person. The test subjects have their strengths and weaknesses.

The hand interaction works well if there is a reference point where these objects should be placed. Examples for this are the toast in the toaster, the pie in the microwave, or the mugs by the coffee machine. The situation is different, however, with objects that do not have a storage destination. This is the case with the remote control. The remote gets stuck on the subject's finger. In some cases, even when a button is pressed directly. What makes this scene special is that the remote control can be moved freely, and buttons must be pressed. This scene is very revealing and provides very clear results. What the hand interaction lacks is a method for freely grabbing and releasing without other reference points. Such a method would prevent objects hanging on the finger. The movement of grabbing an object makes the index finger bend. Accordingly, the implementation of this could be as followed. Instead of checking the curvature of the finger, as in the interaction with the pointer and head, it could be checked whether the thumb and index finger are touching.

Another thing that stood out in this scene is that an object cannot be held, and a button pressed with the other hand at the same time. This means that only one position of interaction is handed over. The implementation of a two-handed interaction would make experiences with scenes like with a remote control much more natural. In this case, the MRTK can also be used for this purpose, as Microsoft provides two-handed interaction as well as scaling or rotating, as already mentioned in chapter 2.6.

The results of this study provide that the hand interaction is particularly well suited for pressing buttons or placing objects in a designated place. Small buttons in particular are no obstacle. However, a function for grasping would be advisable here. The pointer interaction is well suited for moving objects that are further away. The head interaction is rather unsuitable for interacting with small objects. Compared to the other interactions, this interaction requires the least effort for moving objects.

8 Conclusion and Outlook

The motivation at the beginning of the bachelor thesis is to implement interactions with which the virtual prototypes of the Vivian Framework can be operated in Mixed Reality with the HoloLens2 and to evaluate them.

Within the scope of this bachelor thesis, three interactions are

created. A hand interaction, pointer interaction and head interaction. The evaluation of these interactions in a usability study involves two groups. One group intuitively exploring the interactions, while the other group receives an instruction on how to carry out the interactions.

In summary, the results are as follows. During the six scenes tested, a difference between the two groups is apparent. The group with instruction uses the pointer and head interaction more consciously and recognises what actions are triggered when they are done unintentionally. Both groups feel that hand interaction is the most natural and favour it, even if they can handle the others well.

As an outlook, it can be said that the interactions need further work to operate the prototypes more precisely and to prevent objects from disappearing. The usability study is a good basis for further development and offers a good insight into the approach of the test persons, as well as their intuitive gestures, which should be considered when proceeding further.

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Appendix

Pre-Session-Interview Answers

Ich habe die Datenschutz-Hinweise erhalten. Ich willige ein, dass meine Daten, die ich in der Umfrage angebe zum Zweck der Durchführung der S...nymisierter Form veröffentlicht werden dürfen.

10 Antworten

Wie alt sind Sie?

10 Antworten

Beschäftigen Sie sich beruflich oder privat viel mit Technik? Z. B.: PC, Spielekonsole, andere technische Geräte.

10 Antworten

Wie erfahren sind Sie mit Mixed Reality?

10 Antworten

Wenn Sie bereits Erfahrungen mit Mixed Reality haben, wie waren diese?

8 Antworten

In Erfahrung mit VR, Motion Sickness erlebt

Snapchat

Ich entwickle Software / Games für Virtual Reality und spiele ab und an VR Spiele

Pokemon Go, aber hab es schnell wieder ausgeschaltet

AR App auf dem Handy, Head-up Display Auto, Digitale Anzeige in Kamerasucher

Snapchat, Oculus Rift

Verschiedene Usability Tests als Probandin

keine, weiß nicht was das ist

Post-Session-Interview Group A Answers

Ich habe die Datenschutz-Hinweise erhalten. Ich willige ein, dass meine Daten, die ich in der Umfrage angebe zum Zweck der Durchführung der S...nymisierter Form veröffentlicht werden dürfen.

5 Antworten

Finden Sie die Bedienweise der Prototypen intuitiv?

5 Antworten

Könnten Sie sich an die Bedienweise gewöhnen?

5 Antworten

Welche der folgenden Interaktionsmöglichkeiten hat/haben sich am natürlichsten angefühlt?

5 Antworten

Welche Aussagen bezüglich der Einführung am Anfang treffen auf Sie zu?

5 Antworten

Hätten Sie gerne mehr Unterstützung gehabt?

5 Antworten

Was hätte Ihnen das Erlebnis angenehmer gestaltet?

5 Antworten

mehr Erklärung, wie ich die Sachen bedienen muss

Intuitives Ablegen/Loslassen, Gegenstände sollten nicht verschwinden

Es sollte eher angepasst sein an natürliche Interaktion mit Gegenständen; also mit der Hand "greifen" sollte auch hier einen Gegenstand problemlos greifen. "Zurück-zum-Menü-Buttons" antippen hat bei mir auch nicht gut funktioniert.

Mehr Audio bzw. visuelles Feedback

Zu wissen was passiert, komische Ereignisse erklärt bekommen. #Wenn so etwas passiert wie "Tasse verschwidet" wäre es gut zu wissen wieso. Außerdem führen manche Bewegungen zu Ereignissen und dann plötzlich wieder nicht, das ist auch etwas merkwürdig.

Könnten Tests mit virtuellen Prototypen mit physischen Prototypen mithalten?

5 Antworten

Was hat Ihnen gut gefallen?

5 Antworten

Nichts, nichts hat funktioniert, die Brille ist gefühlt nicht hinterher gekommen

Dreidimensionalität, "echtes" bedienen

Mir hat gut gefallen, dass die echte Welt mit zusätzlichen Objekten erweitert wurde. Manche Bedienelemente waren für mich einfach und intuitiv. Zum Beispiel das Navi im Auto, weil man es genau wie in echt auch bedienen kann (per "touch")

Alltägliche Geräte, man kennt sich aus es ist intuitiv, Handinteraktion ohne Controller war sehr angenehm

Audio Feedback vom Fernseher

Fliegende Toasts

Mal eine Mixed Reality Umgebung zu erleben

Was hat Ihnen schlecht gefallen?

5 Antworten

Alles, es war sehr frustrierend, dass fast nichts geklappt hat. Die Objekte waren nicht gut zu bedienen.

Verschwinden von Objekten, Probleme beim Loslassen

Das Greifen hat bei mir nicht gut geklappt, weil es für mich am Anfang sehr schwer zu verstehen war wo meine Objekte plötzlich sind. Das hat auch das Probieren und üben für mich schwer gemacht, da meine Objekte plötzlich weg waren.

- Motion Sickness am Ende
- Zu wenig Audio Feedback
- Szene im Auto wäre schöner mit einem Stuhl gewesen, Positionierung im Auto etwas ungünstig

manchmal passieren "merkwürdige" Dinge, die für mich nicht erklärbar waren. Z.B. Tasse verschwindet plötzlich und taucht an ganz anderer Stelle wieder auf

Haben Sie weitere Anmerkungen/Anregungen? (optional)

4 Antworten

Hat sich nicht so angefühlt, als ob diese Technik innovativ ist.

Alle Gesten sind intuitiv nur nicht das Loslassen, wie schaltet man um zwischen Handgesten und Laserpointer/Kopfbewegung? Ist nur zufällig passiert

Visueller Effekt in der Mikro, wenn die Mikrowelle angeht, dann stimmen die Lichtverhältnisse nicht mehr im Innenraum der Mikrowelle -> Normalen verkehrt?

Wenn die Bedienung intuitiver und "realer" wird, dann können virtuelle Prototypen evtl. besser mit realen Prototypen mithalten

Post-Session-Interview Group B Answers

Ich habe die Datenschutz-Hinweise erhalten. Ich willige ein, dass meine Daten, die ich in der Umfrage angebe zum Zweck der Durchführung der S...nymisierter Form veröffentlicht werden dürfen.

5 Antworten

Finden Sie die Bedienweise der Prototypen intuitiv?

5 Antworten

Könnten Sie sich an die Bedienweise gewöhnen?

5 Antworten

Welche der folgenden Interaktionsmöglichkeiten hat/haben sich am natürlichsten angefühlt?

5 Antworten

Welche Aussagen bezüglich der Einführung am Anfang treffen auf Sie zu?

5 Antworten

Hätten Sie gerne mehr Unterstützung gehabt?

5 Antworten

Was hätte Ihnen das Erlebnis angenehmer gestaltet?

5 Antworten

Vorkenntnisse wären hilfreich, sind jedoch nicht zwingend erforderlich (zusätzlich zur Erklärung am Anfang), Raum etwas abdunkeln

Nichts, es war sehr angenehm

Es sind oft sehr unerwartete Dinge passiert, zB dass Gegenstände wild umher geflogen sind, das hat es ein bisschen schwierig gestaltet.

Ein Tutorial zu Beginn, um die verschiedenen Interaktionsmöglichkeiten erfolgreich durchzuführen

Eine Einführung/Tutorial mit Übung, wie die Gesten exakt ausgeführt werden

Könnten Tests mit virtuellen Prototypen mit physischen Prototypen mithalten?

5 Antworten

Was hat Ihnen gut gefallen?

5 Antworten

Design, sehr realistisch; Aufgaben realitätsgetreu; gute Hilfestellungen

Der Test mit dem TV, als ich die Fernbedienung in der Hand hielt und dass man alles 3D sehen kann und die erste Bedienung mit dem Finger für z. B. Knöpfe antippen und die zweite Bedienung um Sachen zu bewegen

Die User Experience hat mir sehr gut gefallen.

Die vielfältigen Möglichkeiten mit einem Objekt zu interagieren. Den Einbau von grafischen Elementen in der realen Umgebung.

Die Finger Interaktion mit der offenen Hand ausgeführt hat sich am angenehmsten angefühlt, weil so die Finger nicht so verkrampfen

Was hat Ihnen schlecht gefallen?

5 Antworten

Bedienung per Pointer hat nicht funktioniert, Objekte waren plötzlich weg (Kuchen und Kaffeetasse), Kaffeemaschine Knopf für Kaffee hat nicht funktioniert

Dass die Objekte manchmal verschwinden und es manchmal geruckelt hat

Ab und zu gab es störende Lichtreflexionen (ähnlich eines Regenbogens), dies hat das Bild teilweise sehr gestört. Manchmal wurden ein der beiden Hände falsch mitgetrackt (wenn diese zB nicht geschlossen war).

Leichte Verzögerung zwischen Interaktion und der Grafik. Das Verschwinden bzw. nicht schnelles wiederfinden von Objekten durch falsche Ausführung.

Ich konnte die Kopf-Interaktion und den Laserpointer kaum voneinander unterscheiden. V.a. weil man bei der Kopf-Interaktion kein visuelles Feedback bekommt.

Haben Sie weitere Anmerkungen/Anregungen? (optional)

3 Antworten

Testszene: Feedback ob zb Slider am Finger hängen, durch Farbwechsel beispielsweise; allgemein mehr Audio hinzufügen (Kaffeegeräusch, Toast fertig..)

Beim Auto würde ich vllt die Auswahl der Icons noch einmal überdenken.

Der Laser-Pointer reagiert bereits bei der kleinsten Krümmung des Fingers. Diese Interaktion wäre leichter durchzuführen, wenn sie erst bei einer starken Fingerkrümmung reagiert.

Observations

Group A (without instruction)	Toaster	Microwave
P.1	<p>Finger position curved all the time which unintentionally prevents finger interaction. First toast inserted into the toaster with the pointer. Unintentional use of head interaction. First toast unintentionally taken out again, how could not be seen. Second toast inserted with the head interaction. Person operated very roughly and imprecisely. Live tracking disturbed, therefore hardly any support possible.</p>	<p>Switching on with the finger. Problems opening the door. When grasping the cup through a gap, the door then opened completely. Removed cup with finger. Cake with finger in microwave, closed and switched on.</p>
P.2	<p>First toast quickly in with the hand and immediately out again due to the curvature of the finger. Second attempt, toast disappears repeatedly when closing the hand while trying to grasp. Toast hangs on the head. Livestream transmission not possible. Technical difficulties.</p>	<p>Switching on with your finger. Opening the microwave with the pointer. Removing the cup with head then it hangs on the finger. Cake good with finger. Door almost completely closed. When closing the door, removed the cake and lost it.</p>
P.3	<p>Toast moved directly with the head. Toast disappeared when touched. Toaster switch moved a little with the head, then with the finger but not smoothly. Second attempt. Toast inserted - interaction with head - unintentional. Toast and hand interruptions. Toast inserted again with the head. Switching on the toaster with the finger directly succeeded. Toast from the toaster hangs on the head and disappears.</p>	<p>Switching on with the finger. Opening the door and removing the cup, with the head. Cake at the pointer and disappeared. Closing the door with the pointer</p>
P.4	<p>Toast direkt mit dem Finger rein und direkt mit dem Kopf wieder raus. Toast mit Finger erfolgreich rein. Drehen des Knopfs nicht erfolgreich. Beim Einschalten Toast entfernt.</p>	<p>Switching on with the finger. Opening and closing the door with the head. Cake inserted with pointer and door closed with pointer.</p>
P.5	<p>Toast disappeared while grasping. Two toasts inserted with pointer. Turned knob with finger and switched on.</p>	<p>Switch on with finger. Door opened with pointer. Cup jumped to the side when removed. Cake gripped with finger and lost during insertion. Cake moved with head. Cake lost. Cake moved with head. Cake gripped with pointer and inserted. Difficulty closing door, ultimately with hand.</p>

Group A (without instruction)	Coffee Machine	Remote	Car-Infotainment	Test Scene
P.1	Cup jumps away when touched, then briefly at the head. Test without the cup. Switched on and made coffee.	Remote control power button stuck directly on finger. Stuck in the air without reaction.	Finger interaction. Worked straight away.	Interaction only with the finger. Limited operation of all components. Hand tracking not correct. Tracked hand next to real one.
P.2	Problem-free with the finger.	Directly switched on. Try to hold remote control and switch channels at the same time. Channel switched.	Finger interaction. Worked straight away.	Cube hangs on finger. Slider moves and knobs a little. Buttons first without reaction, then ragged. After a short time well operated.
P.3	Switching on with the finger. Cup gripped with the head, intentionally and successfully.	Hand tracking dropouts. Switch on with finger. Hangs on finger.	Finger interaction. Worked straight away.	With finger: Slider not moved. Rotary knob turned. Buttons no reaction. With pointer: Cube rotated and a slider moved.
P.4	Interaction with the finger.	Switch on with the finger. Hangs on finger. Remote control disappeared.	Finger interaction.	With finger: Slider moved. Turned knob. Buttons pressed.
P.5	Interaction with the finger. Switching on only successful after a few attempts. Cup moved with head, finally lost. Pressing button directly successful this time.	Remote control hangs on finger. Switched on. Station changed.	Finger interaction. Severe picture interruptions. Inexplicable how the channel changed. Navigation to the travel information worked directly.	With finger: Slider moved. Rotary knob turned briefly. Buttons pressed.

Group B (with instruction)	Toaster	Microwave
P.1	Interaction with finger. Obstacle-free. Successful.	Switched on with finger. Door opened with head. Difficulty grasping cup. Cake lost. Instead, placed cup in microwave with finger and closed door with finger and switched on.
P.2	Toast gripped with finger, not inserted. Toast moved with head, not inserted. Toast moved with finger, then with head, lost when inserted. Knob turned with finger. Toast moved with pointer and successfully inserted. Toaster switched on with finger.	With finger: Switched on with finger, door opened, cup taken out. With head: Cake deliberately moved, lost. With pointer: Cake placed in microwave, door closed.
P.3	Toast unintentionally moved with head, inserted with finger. Second toast inserted with pointer. Toast out again. Toast inserted with pointer, initially having difficulty turning the toast to insert it. Then out again. With finger: knob turned. With head: switched on.	With finger: Switched on With head: Door open, door closed With pointer: Cake put in microwave, cup put away, cake put in. Difficulties closing the door
P.4	When grasping, slippery toast. With finger: Gripping and inserting the toast. Knob turned. Switched on.	With finger: switched on. Door closed. With pointer: Door open. Cup jumped out of the microwave when grasped. With head: cake held briefly, then disappeared. Cake moved deliberately. Cake repeatedly disappeared when placed in the microwave. Cup placed in microwave with pointer.
P.5	With finger: Toast inserted and directly lost. Unconscious movement with pointer or head. (Natural body holding with hands in front of body). Great confusion about interactions. Toast inserted with finger and taken out directly. Turned knob with finger. Difficulty turning on, only moved briefly by mistake.	With finger: switched on. Door opened. Cup out. Cake inserted. Door closed. Switched on.

Group B (with instruction)	Coffee Machine	Remote	Car-Infotainment	Test Scene
P.1	Finger first moved too deep in coffee machine when pressing button. Cup moved with finger, then lost. It was not possible to make coffee because the coffee machine went out in the meantime, but this was only visible in the photos.	Remote control caught on finger directly while switching. Successfully clicked through the channels.	Finger interaction. Radio station change, no reaction. Image dropout. Difficulty pressing.	With finger: button printed, turned. Slider barely moved. Finger partially inserted deep into the object. Pointer and head interaction not successful.
P.2	Interaction with the finger	Remote control hangs on finger. Switched on with pointer. Switch channel with finger.	Finger interaction. (Try with the pointer.)	With finger: button pressed, turned. Slider not moved at first, then good. (Try with the pointer and head)
P.3	With head: cup moved With finger: Buttons pressed	Uncoordinated movement and disappearance of the remote control when trying to interact. No reaction of the power button.	Finger interaction. At first, no reaction when changing the radio station.	With pointer: Slider moved. Knob turned. With finger: Knob turned unintentionally. Knob pressed. Small boxes moved. With head: Box moved by unplanned hand.
P.4	With finger: Cup moved. Buttons pressed. Difficulty putting the cup down.	Interaction with finger. Initial difficulties positioning the remote control. Successfully switched through the channels.	Finger interaction. Worked straight away.	With finger: turned dice. Buttons pressed, Slider and knob movement with finger and pointer failed.
P.5	With finger: Cup moved. Buttons pressed. Difficulty putting the cup down.	Remote control hangs on finger. Switched on and toggled with finger.	Finger interaction. Selecting travel information probably by accidentally triggering the head interaction.	With finger: Pressed buttons, moved slider, turned knob, moved cube and got stuck on it. With pointer: Knob moved. With head: small cube moved. Person does not recognise the difference between pointer and head interaction.